

SWOT Analysis of the Digital Economy in Indonesia

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Extended Abstract

Digitalization is the process of transforming analog information into digital form. This process is occurring rapidly around the world, and it is essential for global economic competitiveness, innovation, and improved quality of life. Countries that do not embrace digitalization will be at a disadvantage in the global economy (Wade, 2015). Indonesia is one of the largest economies in Southeast Asia and its economy has grown rapidly in recent years (The World Bank, 2023). The country is predicted to emerge as ASEAN's largest digital economy (Das, 2016). To know Indonesia's readiness to become the largest digital economy country, this research studies the state of the digital economy in Indonesia, covering its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT).

Indonesia is a fascinating country with a rich history, diverse culture, and vibrant economy. It is the largest archipelagic country in the world with an area of 1,904,569 km² (United Nations, 2021), and the country with the sixth most islands in the world, 17,504 islands (World Atlas, 2023). With a population of over 276 million people, Indonesia is the fourth most populous country in the world (WIPO, 2022). The population is diverse, with over 1,300 ethnic groups and over 700 languages spoken (Indonesia, 2011). The economy is heavily reliant on natural resources, such as oil, gas, and minerals. Indonesia also exports a lot of agricultural products like palm oil, rubber, and coffee (Britannica, 2023). Indonesia is a popular tourist destination, attracting over ten million visitors each year. There are number of UNESCO World Heritage Sites in Indonesia. It is home to not only historical and cultural sites but also natural sites.

Strengths

With a GDP of \$3530.3 billion, Indonesia has a notably high GDP (WIPO, 2022). The largest driver of Indonesia's economy is driven by strong domestic consumption, accounting for over 50% of GDP. Consumer spending has increased due to the growth of the middle class and rising disposable incomes. The next driver is the growth of global demand for export commodities, such as oil, gas, minerals, and agricultural products. It increased Indonesia's revenue from exports. The third driver is investment. The government has implemented policies to attract foreign direct investment, particularly in infrastructure and manufacturing sectors (The World Bank, 2023).

Indonesia scores relatively high on the Business Environment Indicator, suggesting favourable conditions for businesses. The potential of being emerging market has put Indonesia as a member of G20. Indonesia has 2,489 startups (Startup Ranking, 2023) and 65,465,497 MSMEs (Statista, 2023). Indonesia's Growth of Innovative Companies score is 63.8 (WEF, 2019), which is only 3.2 points lower than Singapore. Israel is the country with the highest score of 80.8. Meanwhile, Indonesia Companies

Embracing Disruptive ideas score is 55.5. Israel has the highest score, namely 68.5. Even though these two scores are still low, these scores show that Indonesia can compete with developed countries.

With a large population, Indonesia has a significant consumer base and potential workforce. Almost 50% of the population is around 20-39 years old (Kominfo a, 2022) (Kominfo b, 2022). The country reported 353.8 million cellular mobile connections, exceeding the total population, at a rate of 128.0% (Kemp, 2023). More than 88% of internet users are active on social media accounts. Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp are the most popular platforms (Kemp, 2023). These numbers point to a high level of mobile connectivity and a significant penetration of social media.

Weaknesses

Indonesia Digitization Index (DiGiX) 2022 is 0.57 (Cámara, 2022). This score is far from Singapore (0.93) and Denmark (1). Even though, has extremely high GDP, Indonesia has low GDP per capita, \$ 12967, while the GDP per capita of Denmark is \$ 63405 and Singapore is 107677 (WIPO, 2022). It shown that inequality of wealth distribution associated with the ability to use Information and Communication Technology (ICT) (Rahman, 2012).

Indonesia has the largest population of Internet users, 212.9 million. However, the Internet penetration rate is still under the regional average among Southeast Asian countries, 77.0% of the total population (Onitsuka, 2018). Indonesia scores quite low for ICT Use (57.8) (WIPO, 2022) and ICT Adoption (55.4) (WEF, 2019). The highest scores for ICT Use and ICT Adoption are 89.1 (Iceland) and 92.8 (Republic of Korea), respectively.

There is also a significant rural-urban divide in digital access and usage. Even though Indonesia has made significant progress in expanding its digital infrastructure, particularly in recent years, there is still a significant portion of the population without access, especially in rural and remote areas. Rural areas often have limited internet access and infrastructure, because most development is concentrated on the Java Island, where the capital city is located (Kartiasih, 2023). Moreover, the large number of islands owned by Indonesia provides its own challenges in achieving equitable development.

Unequal development can have an impact on unequal access to education. Digital skills and literacy are lower among rural residents. It affects low score on Digital skills Among Active Population, namely 58.5, where the highest score for this indicator was 80.5 (Finland) (WEF, 2019). The majority of the Indonesian population only have a secondary education (Kominfo a, 2022) (Kominfo b, 2022) and are housewives (Kominfo a, 2022). Only 19.4% of student Graduating in Science and Engineering (WIPO, 2022); 20% of respondents have attended training (Kominfo b, 2022); and 7.7% of firms offer formal training (WIPO, 2022).

Unequal access to education might associated with Human Development Index (HDI) and Human Capital Index (HCI). Indonesia's HDI and HCI is quite low around 0.7 (UNDP, 2023) and 54 (The World Bank, 2020), respectively. Meanwhile, Denmark can achieve 0.948 for HDI and Singapore can achieve 88 for HCI.

Cybersecurity is a growing concern in Indonesia, as the country becomes increasingly reliant on digital technologies. Just over half of Indonesian businesses reported experiencing a cyber incident (52%), while the primary concern is data loss (82%) (Jackson, 2022)

Indonesia's score for Government's Online Service is also quite low, namely 68.2, compared to the Republic of Korea which received a perfect score of 100 (WIPO, 2022). This could be because Indonesia received very low scores for Regulatory Environment and Incidence of Corruption, namely 21.8 (WIPO,

2022) and 38.0 (WEF, 2019), respectively. The highest scores for Regulatory Environment and Incidence of Corruption, namely 98.7 (Singapore) and 88 (Denmark), respectively. The government must solve these problems first in order to develop the country and provide good services.

Opportunities

Due to its wealth in agricultural goods, history, and culture, Indonesia can strengthen its economy by diversifying its sources of income and lowering its dependency on the export of commodities. With an extremely high GDP, Indonesia can allocate funds wisely to build infrastructure, provide free ICT to the community, develop e-government, and improve the quality of education. For Indonesia, investment in Infrastructure is ensuring widespread access to various and reliable digital technologies and services for all citizens therefore It can increase digital inclusion. Digital infrastructure, such as broadband internet and mobile networks, is essential for the development of the digital economy. Digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence and cloud computing, can be used to improve productivity, efficiency, and innovation. By investing in education and skills training, HDI and HCI can be improved. Digital talents are in high demand in Indonesia, particularly in areas such as Software Development, Data Analysis, and Cybersecurity. Moreover, Indonesia has an abundance of data that can be used to drive innovation and improve decision-making in various sectors. The strong entrepreneurial culture in Indonesia can be an opportunity to promote digital entrepreneurship by providing support and resources to startups and small businesses. Despite facing challenges, the digitalization of MSMEs has the potential to significantly contribute to economic growth. MSMEs can improve operational efficiency and expand their market reach by implementing digital tools. An increasing number of Indonesians are utilizing mobile wallets and other digital financial services, demonstrating the country's high fintech adoption. The development of e-government in Indonesia can potentially speed up the administrative processes and increase transparency, so that services for citizens can be improved, economic turnover can be accelerated, and corruption can be minimized. This is expected to boost GDP per capita and people's well-being. Indonesia is well-positioned for digital transformation, as seen by its 70% internet penetration rate and large youth population who are technologically literate (Onitsuka, 2018). The country can leverage the technological fluency and aspirations of its youth to drive demand for digital services.

Threats

While the digital economy in Indonesia is growing, there is a need for the regulatory system to catch up to support and sustain this growth. The threats to cybersecurity are growing along with the digital economy. Indonesia needs to strengthen its cybersecurity capabilities to protect its critical infrastructure and data from cyberattacks. To protect the privacy of its citizens and ensure that their data is used responsibly Indonesia must establish a strong regulation for data privacy. Digital technologies can be misused for malicious purposes, such as spreading misinformation, hate speech, and cybercrime. Indonesia must create mechanisms to address these threats. The digital economy could lead to job displacement in some sectors as jobs are automated or outsourced. Indonesia needs to develop policies to support workers who are affected by technological change.

Conclusion

Digitalization significantly influences a country's economic growth and competitiveness. While growth and development in Indonesia's digitalization state have been rapid, there are still significant challenges and inequalities. As can be seen from the above study, Indonesia's most dominant weakness related to the digital economy is its low of DiGiX score, GDP per capita, Human Development

Index, digital infrastructure, and digital skills or literacy. Countries with high DiGiX scores, such as Denmark and Singapore, also have high scores for those components. Thus, GDP per capita, Human Development Index, digital infrastructure, and digital skills or literacy are all indirectly correlated with the DiGiX score. On the other hand, Indonesia has strengths in GDP, population, and Business environment. To become the largest digital economy country, Indonesia needs to be able to capitalize on its strengths to overcome its weaknesses without ignoring the threats posed by the digital economy. As Indonesia's digitalization index rises, we can expect to see positive impacts on the economy, human development, and social inclusion.

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